

Synthesis and DFT studies of a novel ESIPT 2-(2'-Hydroxyphenyl)-1H-benzimidazole derivative

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Abstract

Molecules having excited state intramolecular proton transfer (ESIPT) show characteristic properties like large Stokes shift and dual fluorescence emission. Such molecules are used in various fields as lasers, fluorescence probes, sensors, and optical devices. 2-(2'-hydroxyphenyl)-1H-benzimidazole (HBL) and its analogues are a family of widely studied ESIPT fluorophores. In the present work, we have tuned HBL by another proton donating site to further enhance its Stokes shift. The novel HBL derivative, 2-(1H-benzimidazol-2-yl)-4-(2-hydroxybenzylideneamino) phenol, was synthesized and the structure was confirmed using ¹H NMR spectroscopy. Feasibility of proton transfer was elucidated by potential energy scan (PES) in ground state on a pair of oxygen-hydrogen using Density Functional Theory (DFT). The calculations carried out using long range corrected functional CAM-B3LYP and 6-31 g(d, p) basis set in presence of methanol environment adopted by PCM show least probability of proton transfer in the ground state. However, back proton transfer from excited state to ground state can happen easily. UV-Vis absorption spectrum obtained by the same method shows three peaks at 287, 313 and 331 nm, due to π - π^* transition of benzene ring, cis-enol and trans-enol conformations, respectively.

Key words: ESIPT, DFT, PES